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ASSESSING THE POTENTIAL OF CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS CONTENT IN EUROPEAN STEEL SLAG

Daniel MONFORT¹, Audrey PHILIPPE¹, Basile GUTH¹, Nourredine MENAD¹, Liesbet VAN DEN ABEELE², Lorena SANZ², Joren VAN STEE², Sonia MARTINS DA CUNHA³, José MOGOLLON³, Gorazd ZIBRET⁴ and Spela BAVEC⁴

¹ BRGM, French geological survey, 45060 Orléans, France

² VITO, 2400 Mol, Belgium

³ CML, Institute of Environmental Sciences - Leiden University, 2300 RA Leiden, Netherlands

⁴ Geo-ZS, Geological survey from Slovenia, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia

d.monfortcliment@brgm.fr

Introduction

In the context of the Critical Raw Materials (CRM) Act for the EU, the European Commission is evaluating the content and the potential quantity available for recycling of CRMs in various secondary sources from urban mine and other flows such as mining wastes or industrial wastes. Steel slag production, which represents a significant volume of waste annually in Europe, is being considered as a potential secondary supply source for several CRMs in the framework of Horizon Europe project FutuRaM. In terms of metal recovery, over the last 20 years several research projects in Europe investigated and developed methods for the recovery of metals contained in ferrous slags such as Extravan (2014-2017), CHROMIC (2017-2020) or Hypass (ended in 2021). The goal of the present work is to assess and estimate the potential CRM recoverable contained in European steel slags produced currently and in the future.

Steel slag composition and current production

In this work, a literature review of 25 articles and references was carried out, providing data on the metal content of various types of iron & steel slags for more than 60 different samples: Blast Furnace (BF), Electric Arc Furnace (EAF), Basic Oxygen Furnace (BOF), argon oxygen decarburisation (AOD) and ladle slags (LDS). A category for historical and legacy sites with slag heaps was also included (Regeneratis and Hypass projects). The information about the steel types (stainless steel, carbon steel) was collected when available. As dealing with high amounts and a wide range of origins (over 500 steel production sites) and thus, contents, it is relevant to work with average values as the statistical expected annual flow. This review provides an overview of the content distribution, especially on average, maximum and minimal content measured in different steel slags worldwide. The average composition of slags, obtained by merging a variety of sources, can be seen in Figure 1. Based on the 2023 EU CRM list, vanadium

and titanium show relatively high concentrations in BOF with grades comparable or higher for vanadium to those found in primary ores¹. Chromium also exhibits significant content in EAF slags, although it is not classified as critical on the EU's 2023 list and compared to primary ores slag grade is much lower. BF metal content is very low.

Figure 1: Average chemical composition for certain elements of EAF and BOF slags

In terms of slags flows, Euroslag² assess annually the slag production in Europe, but they have difficulties to get the entire information for all EU countries. In 2018, they estimated that EU27+UK generated 25.2 Mt blast furnace slags and 22.6 Mt steelmaking plants slags (BOF+EAF+others). Euroslag and World Steel³ statistics provide information that makes it possible to calculate a ratio for slag production, BF produces 280 kg of slag/t hot metal production and BOF and EAF have a ratio around 90 kg slag/ steel production. Those values are lower than ratios proposed by Piemonti et al⁴ (180 kg for EAF and 150 kg for BOF), indicating maybe that the Euroslag data do not cover all the slag production.

Table 1: Chemical composition in wt% for chromium, vanadium and titanium after the literature review. Between parenthesis mean values

El.	BOF slag	EAF slag	Ladle slag	Mining ore grade ¹
V	0.077 to 2.7 (1.4)	0.031 to 0.09 (0.09)	0.028 to 0.28 (0.15)	0.12
Cr	0.05 to 3.4 (0.9)	0.19 to 3.3 (1.2)	0.007 to 0.33 (0.15)	27
Ti	0.4 to 1.4 (0.87)	0.24 to 1.3 (0.6)	0.08 to 0.53 (0.23)	1.59

Future steel slag flows in Europe

Future production of steel slags in Europe was modelled based on steel production foresight. Even though the production of steel in the future can be discussed and modelled integrating macroeconomic parameters, it was decided to consider a constant production of steel in Europe taking as reference the mean value of the production of steel observed between 2018 and 2023 based on World Steel³ and Eurofer⁵ data. This

period integrates Covid-19 and energy crisis after Ukraine’s war, two events that impacted strongly the European steel production. The possibility of new steelmaking plants from greenfield in Europe was not considered as it does not appear clearly in current steel industry roadmap.

Three scenarios were considered for future assessments:

The first one is a “business-as-usual” (BAU) scenario based on the average slag production over the past 5 years (as reported in Eurofer⁵ annual reports). The second scenario called “Recovery” considers that Europe develops a higher recycling and recovery performance. In terms of steel production it means that there is a substitution from the integral cycle (BF/BOF) to the electric cycle (EAF), with changes in slag composition, but maintaining a global steel production constant. Finally, the third scenario, called “Circular”, is more optimistic and simulates a more circular economy more based in reuse and refurbishment, with an induced reduction of metal recycling. This last scenario is the more challenging as there are currently very few indicators and public statistics about reuse for metals.

In all the scenarios the slag is collected and then recovered, with different methods such as magnetic separation, slag concentration, or landfilled. Other slags uses (cement, aggregates) are also considered as current situation of slag valorisation. A material flow analysis (MFA) was conducted for the three scenarios to calculate the mass of CRM that is recovered. Knowing the average content of CRMs in the different slag types, as well as their material flows allows to estimate the CRM annual quantity that could be recovered.

Figure 2: System boundaries of steel slag recovery as assessed in present study

For metals such as vanadium the content in BOF slag (around 7 Mt/y in BAU scenario) can vary between 3% and 0.077%, that is between 200 kt/y and 5 kt/y of vanadium. The maximal value of vanadium content is clearly overestimated, indeed slags is the direct consequence of the primary ore composition used in the production, which is in general much lower. For comparison, the global primary production of vanadium is 91 kt/y⁶.

CRM recovery in steel slags

The central question driving the European CRM Act is: "What is the real potential of secondary sources in terms of CRM supply?" A review of major metal recovery technologies was recently addressed⁷ providing an excellent overview of existing methods, though many are still at the laboratory or pilot scale, all the methodologies applied are hydrometallurgy processes. For chromium they found a recovery rate between 68 and 95%, for vanadium between 28 and 90% and for titanium between 62 and 98%. Those references give an overview of the potential recovery in the field of research and development but this literature review contain works and studies with very different technological readiness level. The reality is that few research projects succeed to upscale metal recovery solutions. We can cite in the field of industrial projects, in Finland, the Novana⁸ project that plans to recover 9 kt/year of vanadium pentoxide with a treatment to steels slags containing 3.9% V₂O₅ (2.2% V metal content). Pilot Plant testing of the selected flowsheet was completed and resulted in product purities of greater than 99.5% V₂O₅ with maximum vanadium recoveries exceeding 75%. Novana are in partnership with steel mills in Finland and Sweden.

Conclusions

Steel slag represent a big volume of annual wastes in Europe (around 35 Mt/year) where bulk materials solutions are necessary (aggregates, cement, *etc.*). Hydrometallurgy processes for critical raw materials recovery (V, Ti, Cr...) have been developed in the Research and Development field the recent years but the industrial upscaling of those projects remains difficult. Despite the strategic and economic importance of CRMs contained in these slag flows, they represent a low percentage (~1%) and the management of the rest of the flow is a major issue. However, the total quantity of certain CRM such as V or Ti contained in all slag flows represent a very important quantity that requires a more accurate characterisation and estimation as only a portion of certain slags have a high/valuable content. Initiatives such as the vanadium recovery project in Finland show that CRM potential recovery projects can emerge if certain conditions are met: high CRM content in the initial slag, constant slag flow for a certain period, existence of mature recovery technology and solution for managing the remaining flow.

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